

A STUDY ON IMPACT OF ADVERTISING CLUTTER TOWARDS CONSUMER PURCHASE BEHAVIOUR IN URBAN AREAS

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Abstract:

This Paper overwhelming deals with several complications and challenges on clutter promotions which are stimulate and driving an individual behaviour in terms of consumerism in direct and indirect market environment in urban premises. For that complicating process deciding to commence and spot the sound wisdom in this corridor. Asses the attributes of consumer market, sales technique, types of advertisements, perception and personal buying behaviour in this track. The global market is a complex one that involves a large amount of equipment and terminologies that can be assist to target consumers in a predominantly transactional process. Media such as Direct Mail, Magazines, Newspapers, TV/radio, co-ops, Telemarketing/Teleservices and the Internet to promote their messages in a persistent manner on daily basis to attract and conquer new customers. In addition, this study will reveal about the factors on enterprises captivate the consumer's minds without their desire despite the consumer reluctant to pay their attention on these promotions. Clutter advertisements are creating a sensational growth in consumerism in the past three decades, attributes which are associating and annotating in promotions will be examined in an in-depth manner in this study.

Introduction:

The impact of advertising clutter as we use it today, which served so well the needs of new townships. Today, this geographical justification for cluttering and marketing has been replaced by our needs for much more cost-effective, measurable and reliable ways of managing customers. Technology has made it too easy for us to communicate directly with urban customers, while changes in segments and media selection have made conventional marketing techniques less effective in getting the response you want from your customers - though of course they are still very powerful in developing and sustaining branding. Direct marketing is a form of marketing that attempts to send its messages directly to consumers, without the use of intervening media. The key principle of cluttering is that at least part of the communication may deal with customer is direct - to named customers. Advertising clutter differs from occasional advertising in that it does place its messages on a third party medium such as a billboard, television or a radio commercial. The marketing of the service or commodity is pitched directly at the consumer. Most of the advertisement is done by agencies whose only function is to manage and perform advertising, rather than by the advertised entity itself. Direct marketers have been long time customers of computer databases, and they often have very sophisticated criteria of inclusion and exclusion in their mailing lists. Today advertising plays a broader role, that of building a long-term relationship with the customer. Too many advertisements in a time will conquer the customer attention. Especially urban customers have been responding to large amount of promotions towards specific product or brand.

Objectives:

Emphasize the impact of advertising clutter on consumers purchasing behaviour in urban areas and know the various complications and challenges in preferred medias and the reasons for clutter advertisement impacts on comprehensive buying attitude of consumer behaviour.

Review of Literature:

Observing the Consumers' behaviour towards clutter assume significance as it reflects his/her attitude towards the advertised products also, to an extent. The attitude of consumers is generally influenced by the type of advertising exposure and the intensity of attention towards such advertisements. The need for investigating the attitude of consumers towards TV / Radio / Internet advertisements is expressed in many national and international journals. With this notion, reviewed the literature related to consumer attitude and are presented below:

- Dr. Chandrakhanthan and Mrs. Karthika R (2018) made a comprehensive study on pre purchase behaviour of customer and impact of TV advertising. The study focused perception of pre purchase behaviour of customers and also emphasized impacts of TV advertising. (International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics, ISSN 1331-8080)
- Mr. P. Mayil Rajan and Dr. R. Seeni Syed Ibrahim (2018) articulated a study on Factors Influence in Direct Marketing. This study elaborated the significant factors which are influence consumer behaviour. Further this study reveals the growth of digital media, changes in consumer shopping

approach and relationship marketing etc. (Journal of Analysis and Computation, International Peer Reviewed Journal, ISSN 0973- 2861)

- Dr. Chandrakhanthan, Mr. P. Mayilrajan & Mr. A. Prasathkumar (2019) made a comprehensive study on Impact of TV Viewing on behavioral changes on children. This study reveals the behavioural changes which occurs by TV advertisement. Media impact has been clearly stated in this study.(International Journal Of Research Culture Society. ISSN 2456-6683)
- Faraz Ahmad (2014) made a comparative study of TV and Internet advertising. The study focused perception of TV and internet advertising. The study focused perception of TV and Internet. The study found that new age medium, the internet is a more effective medium in marketing information available than TV.
- Abdul Azeem and Zia UL Haq (2012) Investigated the antecedents of consumer attitude towards internet advertisement among three demographic groups students, employees and entrepreneurs. The study identified Entertainment, Information, Credibility, Economy And Value Corruption as the significant predictors of attitude towards advertisement. It was found that entrepreneurs exhibited a positive attitude, whereas the overflow of information made the consumers to be cynical. Further the study stated that there is a gap between attitude and actual purchasing behaviors.
- Usman Daud (2011) studied the impact of TV advertising in changing the lifestyle of Pakistani youth. The study analyzed the parameters such as habits, attitude, tastes, moral standards and found that TV advertisement is changing the lifestyle of both male and female.

Impact of Advertising Clutter in Urban:

Advertising clutter is a concept applied to refer to the very large amount of Advertising; urban people are exposed to, on a daily basis. It can be difficult for advertisers to cut through the clutter to reach potential consumers. New methods of advertising are constantly being developed in an attempt to stay ahead of the curve in the advertising world. Creative, Innovative and aggressive approaches to advertising are expected from most advertising agencies as it can be difficult to reach people with usual means. The quantity of individual messages people is exposed to on a given day varies, but generally people hear advertisements on the radio, see them on television and in print publications, interact with them online, and sometimes receive them in their mailboxes. Many of these contacts are very brief. customers can be overwhelmed by the volume of advertising clutter they see every day that rise above the clutter will gear up.

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Admiring the functions of advertising clutter in the way consumers admit with advertising is important. Viewers developing ad campaigns should think about issues like clutter and ways for reach their target demographic. Researchers observe the way different groups of people interact with advertising and take note of ads that stand out in given demographics, using this information in the development of advertising strategies. Failure to research a particular segmentation well and find out which way to reach that demographic can have expensive impacts for advertisers, such as campaigns that flop when released into the urban market environment. Customers are spending long time away from residence, marketers are investing more money on bringing TV to you: in shopping malls and in grocery stores and advertising reaches people on computers and movie screens. To reach people, advertisers should get much more innovative digitally inserting virtual products within shows and even video games engaging them to the entertainment instead of a break from the entertainment.

Connect with Customers' Emotional Needs:

Specific themes create an emotional chord with the vast majority of the customers in city. These wide appealing subjects can be used in marketing to make the message strike a personal note while generating interest with the widest possible audience.

Impact of Effective Medias:

Medias such as TV, billboards, radio and posters are all completely saturated with marketing messages and competition is high and this makes them costly. Media schedule is usually priced depending on the number of people who are likely to see your advertisement, however it's much more important to be noticed by the right people in urban territories rather than simply playing a game. Guerrilla marketing is a the most braving approaches to advertising. Many ideas have been tried, including illuminating buildings, sponsoring car, or even sky diving into a stadium with a branded parachute. Possibility for PR exposure is high. Experiential marketing involves physical interaction with individuals using live events. If done well, these can be the most powerful marketing medium so are well worth considering. Viral ads require clever thinking and a fair amount of luck - but a successful viral can bring vast amounts of attention to a business or product. Ensure the advertisement is humorous, shocking or likely to generate strong opinions.

Impact of Sense Appealing:

Another way to stand out is by engaging a consumer's senses through touch, smell, sound and sight. These strategies are most often implemented in high traffic areas such as airports, or at retail locations and kiosks. Create extra large and visually appealing images or models of your product. Engage consumers with touchpad computer screens, where they can move objects around and play with certain features. Make the experience enjoyable so they remember the product or company name.

Urban Customer Retention:

Urban shoppers retention on the part of consumers can be achieved by persisting advertising messages and associated images so people remember them. consumers who are most likely to use your products must be targeted either by age, income, certain personality traits, beliefs or lifestyles. Create messages that appeal to your target audience. Include content key benefits consumers can gain by using your products or services. Repeat those messages often through various media, including print and the Internet. unique slogans or catchphrases that stress key benefits. Make it easy for people to recognize advertisements with logos, characters or jingle.

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Consumer Attention for Effective Advertising Clutter:

The consumer's short attention span was something, which the advertising industry has been looking into. This could indicate getting an image to the consumer's attention had become shorter than before due to the immense exposure of all the media that had been available in the present day. Hence, it is very important to choose the one thing to be conveyed due to the time limitation. In particular of the television commercial field, there is no doubt that there was a shift in the commercial trend in order to address the short attention span issue as well. In the early days, all the commercials were 60 seconds long before the 30-second spots were introduced which then brought about the availability of 15-second and 10-second spots as well (White, 2003). Hence, the shrinking attention span of the consumers introduces the shortening of commercial length.

The urban viewers' attention span was something, which the advertising agency has been focusing into. This could indicate getting an image to the consumer's attention had become shorter than before due to the immense exposure of all the media that had been available in the present day. Hence, it is very important to choose the one thing to be conveyed due to the time limitation. In particular, of the television commercial field, there is no doubt that there was a shift in the commercial trend in order to address the short attention span issue as well. In the early days, all the commercials were 60 seconds long before the 30-second spots were introduced which then brought about the availability of 15-second and 10-second spots as well. Hence, the attention span of the consumers introduces the shortening of commercial length.

Media Fragmentation:

Market fragmentation has resulted in media fragmentation because of the alternative media channels available to the consumer and all messages seen as one single message to consumer. Today's educated consumers are being irritated with a bundle of television channels, and a steady stream of new magazines that hit the newsstands every week. Coupled with rising level of ad dodging and the future for some mass media might seem austere. Therefore, advertising has to spread further, covering massive amount of channels to gain the same exposure.

Conclusion:

Consumers Advertising clutter create the huge impact on young people who tend to be adept at using media, constantly online and sceptical are increasingly immune to the clichés of prime-time television and radio.

The disquiet among media viewers, of course, is that an increased number of viewer attention means that each advertisement becomes less effective in getting its message across. A viewer's ability to recall an advertisement goes down by about 45 percent, for example, in commercial breaks with seven or more spots compared to breaks with three or fewer. Generally, the solution for advertising might be to turn back the clock, to a time of sponsorships and fewer commercials. Advertising writers say that the solution is more creative advertising that breaks out from the advertising clutter.

A high quality of repeated advertisements or cluttering are playing a pivotal role to modify the attitudes of city residents in purchase. Most effective and efficient advertisements designed to increase responsiveness or to promote a brand, but not unavoidably to generate clicks or traffic.

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